

THE POTENTIAL AND IMPORTANCE OF DIPLOMATIC ETIQUETTE

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ANNOTATION

The article explores the rule and importance of diplomatic etiquette. Based on the given information, it should be said that diplomatic relations without etiquette will not be as positive as expected. Diplomatic etiquette is a manifestation of good behavior in relations between officials, political and public figures representing their country. Diplomats interact with their counterparts in government, public, and business circles according to long-established rules, deviations from which can lead to unwanted complications in the relationship. The rules of diplomatic etiquette contain certain forms of addressing, correspondence, as well as visits, meetings and talks, diplomatic receptions, etc. They set strict requirements for the appearance of a diplomat, civil servant, businessman. Etiquettes are defined by the Oxford Dictionary as the customary code of polite behavior in society or among members of a particular profession or group. Diplomats represent themselves with professionalism and respect to foster positive relationships and advance the interests of their nation.

Key words: *etiquette, diplomacy, diplomats, diplomatic protocol, diplomatic etiquette, negotiation, ceremony, international relations.*

Introduction. Diplomatic etiquette is the set of rules and customs that guide the behavior of diplomats and government representatives when representing their country

on the international stage. Diplomatic etiquette refers to the protocol and rules of behavior that are followed by diplomats and other government officials when interacting with each other and with foreign dignitaries.

Etiquette is a phenomenon that changes over the course of history and culture, and therefore assumes new forms and shapes. The norms of manners change over time. Social transformations, changes in culture, industrialization, urbanization, dissemination of radio and TV, Internet, mobile phones and the development of other means of communication, as well as increasingly common globalization, have caused a change in living conditions and, as a consequence, the emergence of new customs. This creates new challenges for everyone, especially for persons busy in international and diplomatic missions. It requires a good understanding of foreign cultures and a sense of tact. Knowing and practicing the rules of etiquette allows freely find yourself in a variety of circumstances and minimizes the incivility.

These rules and behaviors are designed to ensure that interactions between different countries and their representatives are respectful and productive and to help prevent misunderstandings or conflicts. Diplomatic etiquette also includes formalized procedures for handling issues such as the presentation of credentials, establishing diplomatic relations, and the accreditation of diplomats.

While in another country, there are specific rules or protocols that a diplomat must observe. A diplomat must observe the protocols and traditions of the host country apart from showing respect for the culture and customs of the country of residence.

A diplomat also must be mindful of body language and nonverbal communication behavior while practicing diplomacy in another country. It is also important for the diplomat to be reliable and punctual, discreet and confidential in communication. Establishing diplomatic ranks and preferences is an important achievement of the diplomatic protocol, because it has caused serious conflicts numerous times in history.

There are three levels in diplomacy which are interconnected but not identical: protocol, ceremony and etiquette. The protocol regulates relations between states and their representatives. The ceremonial serves the organization of official ceremonies,

especially state ones. And the diplomatic etiquette is the observance of principles of behavior and dress in public places. “The principle of priority is an important element in the contacts of all communities. In diplomatic contacts, it occurs primarily during ceremonies, greetings and farewells of guests, making speeches, bursting guests at the table and in the car, raising toasts, serving to the table, etc. The basic criteria of this rule are class and rank, duration of function and such standards as: guest before the host, guest from abroad before the guest from the country, woman before the man (applying the seniority principle), and senior before the younger. We distinguish between personal priority, mission priority and priority within the mission”.

The historical roots of diplomatic protocol come from court etiquette and the traditions of individual countries. The protocol evolved with the development of diplomatic international relations and reached its first summit during the Congress of Vienna in 1815, when international relations took place in such proximity that they required rules. The emergence of the presidency, ceremonial, correspondence, immunities and the establishment of a diplomatic etiquette (unleashing it from a court etiquette), these are the achievements of the European diplomatic policy of the last two centuries. If once the main tools in diplomacy were such savoir-vivre principles as tactfulness, discretion, skills in negotiating, then today diplomatic etiquette and various ceremonies are components of the diplomatic protocol, which employees of diplomatic units must know exactly. The protocol that it became is a collection of traditions and principles derived from the cultural traditions of various countries and was regulated for the first time after the Congress of Vienna primarily as a term for presidency in political relations. After changing the political system in Europe and the principles of redundancy, it was again developed and included in the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations on April 18, 1961.

An important element of the diplomatic protocol is the ceremonial. It is a concept that defines the organization of official ceremonies and a set of rules and customs which are applicable to the preparation of various ceremonies. The ceremony, according to the dictionary, is an official ceremony or rite, according to the established

plan of the people of the ritual. Usually it is a solemn act in keeping with traditional symbolic forms. The diplomatic ceremony includes all norms which are applicable to diplomatic representatives who hold official relations with the head of the state in which they are accredited, as well as the authorities of that state and the norms which are applicable to the mutual relations of those diplomatic representatives operating in the same post. The ceremonial norms have created centuries-old customary traditions and they have established themselves in diplomatic exchange between states, so that today they are one of the major areas of international law.

Etiquette is a phenomenon that changes over the course of history and culture, and therefore assumes new forms and shapes. The norms of manners change over time. Social transformations, changes in culture, industrialization, urbanization, dissemination of radio and TV, Internet, mobile phones and the development of other means of communication, as well as increasingly common globalization, have caused a change in living conditions and, as a consequence, the emergence of new customs. This creates new challenges for everyone, especially for persons busy in international and diplomatic missions. It requires a good understanding of foreign cultures and a sense of tact. Knowing and practicing the rules of etiquette allows freely find yourself in a variety of circumstances and minimizes the incivility.

The contemporary development of communication technologies and increasing relationships via the Internet has also evoked the concept of “netiquette”, i.e. a set of principles of decent behavior on the Internet, a kind of etiquette applicable on the web. Netiquette also plays an important role in the process of international relations and diplomacy. For example, in the event of a high-profile event, a consular or diplomatic mission must notify the residents of its country on its official website of the event and associated recommendations. In addition, electronic correspondence is also used, which is subject to the specific rules in this area. The last type of communication takes the name “email etiquette”.

The practical use of etiquette is already on the border of the concept of “good manners”, which refers to the ability to behave, self-presentation and communication

with other people. The practical etiquette, often appointed, is more rigid and requires the implementation of certain rules of the surrounding society or environment. Another type of etiquette is *savoir-vivre* (“etiquette for the people”), which is intended for the general public and incorporates the principles of good tone (i.e. the ability to behave and behave in relations with other people in accordance with the social rules prevailing in that country, in a given culture or the environment). *Savior-vivre* pays more attention to aspects of everyday and social life: age, gender, family and friendship, social prestige, religious affiliation, party, etc.

As modern technology makes war more costly, negotiations within and outside diplomatic conferences are becoming increasingly important. This PIN Policy Brief analyses the nature and evolution of diplomatic negotiation and the challenges to its effectiveness. It argues that negotiations are vulnerable, unless they are protected by procedural frameworks, comprising rules and conventions, such as those adopted in conference diplomacy conducted by organizations such as the United Nations. This policy brief also raises questions about the future role of diplomatic negotiation processes in a globalizing world in which diplomats are losing their traditional predominance in international relations. It concludes with several recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness, and thereby the significance, of diplomatic negotiation in the future.

In view of the observations above, and focusing on the role of the diplomat as a negotiator, four recommendations are useful.

- First, it would be wise to give researchers and trainers more access to real negotiation processes.
- Second, the diplomatic negotiator might be specialized communicator
- Third, diplomats will have to be a superb manager.
- Diplomatic negotiation itself will have to be more efficient.

Negotiation is as old as human history. Diplomatic negotiation entered the world stage some five millennia ago. Conference diplomacy as a mode of international negotiation has been around for 300 years, yet it established its organizational format

only in the last 100 years. It is therefore a relatively recent phenomenon in human history. It is enormously helpful in protecting the vulnerable process of international negotiation from failure.

When conducting conversations important to keep a low profile and with dignity, not to interrupt the interlocutor, to avoid excessive gesticulation. Of great importance is the culture of speech: the use of literacy literary verbal speed and a rich vocabulary It helps a person to establish itself as a well-read and well-educated diplomat and a partner with whom pleasant to deal with.

In no case should not allow himself such liberties as the use of obscene language while any dispute, to talk with business partners did not develop into open conflict or skirmish.

Conclusion. **Everything you have just learn is seen as formal and diplomatic etiquette in “western” countries(Exception: Nordic countries/Eastern European countries) thus it is absolutely vital that; if you are attending a gathering in a culturally different community to properly inform yourself on the do’s and the don’t’s of their cultural etiquette; as it might differ significantly from previously stated in the article.

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